

CATALYTIC ACETYLATION OF ACETYLENE IN VAPOR PHASE

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Currently, vinyl acetate production in developed countries is carried out in two ways.

Oxidation and etherification of ethylene. The process is based on the reaction between ethylene, acetic acid and oxygen in the presence of a catalyst:

Based on the vapor phase catalytic reaction between acetylene and acetic acid:

The first method is widely used because the cost of ethylene is cheaper compared to acetylene. Currently, cheap sources of acetylene are being found as a by-product of new production processes. Therefore, the production of vinyl acetate from acetylene remains promising.

The core substance (carrier) holding catalysts was prepared using sol-gel technology. Keramzite material was used as a holding core substance (nositel), $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$, $\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ and $\text{ZrO}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ as active components. $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$, $\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ and $\text{ZrO}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ absorbed into keramzite were heated at 350-4000C and treated with glacial acetic acid at 180-2000C. At this time, zinc and cadmium oxides are converted into the corresponding acetates. The structure and properties of the resulting catalysts are given in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Composition and properties of created catalysts

Nº	Composition, mass %	S, m ² /g	Mechanica l strength, MPa	Selectivity to vinyl acetate	Acetic acid conversion, %
1	ZnO·ZrO ₂ /keramzite	150	46,0	74.8	52
2	CdO·ZrO ₂ /keramzite	160,0	52,0	74.3	51.4
3	ZnO·CdO·ZrO₂/keramzite	143,0	50,0	94.5	85.9
4	ZnO·Cr ₂ O ₃ ·ZrO ₂ /keramzite	182,0	43,0	72	72.1
5	ZnO·Fe ₂ O ₃ ·Cr ₂ O ₃ /keramzite	172,0	55,0	67.7	70.9

As can be seen from the table, among the catalysts, the most active and selective is the catalyst containing 15% zinc acetate, 15% cadmium acetate and 1% zirconium nitrate. In this catalyst, the conversion of acetic acid is very high.

The dependence of the activity of the catalyst on the amount of zinc acetate and cadmium acetate was studied. For this, the total amount of zinc acetate and cadmium acetate was changed from 5% to 40% while keeping the ratio of $Zn(CH_3COO)_2$, and $Cd(CH_3COO)_2$ constant at 1:1. Experiments were carried out at 180-185°C and $C_2H_2:CH_3COOH=4:1$ ratio, volume velocity effect at 280 h⁻¹. The obtained results are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Dependence of the activity of the catalyst on the total amount of acetates in its content

As can be seen from the data presented in Figure 1, the yield of vinyl acetate increases when the sum of the concentrations of $Zn(CH_3COO)_2$, and $Cd(CH_3COO)_2$ in the catalyst increases to 30-35%. When the total amount of $Zn(CH_3COO)_2$, and $Cd(CH_3COO)_2$ in the catalyst increases from 35% to 40%, the yield of vinyl acetate decreases.

Under the above conditions, the life of the catalyst is 2200 hours. Much work has been published on the vapor phase synthesis of vinyl acetate, with zinc acetate adsorbed on activated carbon at 155–200°C and acetylene:acetic acid mole ratios ranging from 2:1 to 6:1 conducted at atmospheric pressure.

Table 2. Vinyl acetate yield and equilibrium constant

T, °C	T, K	lgK _p	K _p	α
155-170	428-443	1.2	52.3	0.83
180-185	453-458	1,53	65.2	0,91
190-200	463-473	0,88	8.3	0,62

In order to interpret the obtained experimental data, it is necessary to find kinetic equations that satisfy the changes of parameters (reaction rate, reaction rate constant, adsorption coefficient and partial pressure) in a wide range.

In the process of synthesis of vinyl acetate, in addition to the main reaction, the following additional reactions take place:

In order to avoid additional reactions, the reaction is carried out in the presence of a large amount of acetylene.

The process of obtaining vinyl acetate from acetylene and acetic acid can be represented by the following general equation:

The reaction takes place at 180-185°C and normal atmospheric pressure.

Table 3. Material balance of vinyl acetate production

$$C_2H_2 \div CH_3COOH = 4:1; \quad V_{C_2H_2} = 280 \text{ hour}^{-1}$$

$$K_{CH_3COOH} = 85,4\%; \quad K_{CH_3COOH} \rightarrow BA(94.5); \quad \text{kat} : ZnO \cdot CdO \cdot ZrO_2 / \text{keramzite}$$

Components	Up to the reactor		After the reactor	
	kg/hour	kmol/hour	kg/hour	kmol/hour
Technical acetylene, from which	338,542			
Pure acetylene	325	12,5	241,54	9,29
Attachments	13,542		13,542	
Glacial acetic acid (96%) of this	195,3125			
Pure acetic acid	187,5	3,125	27,375	0,456
N ₂ O	7,8125	0,434	-	-
Vinyl acetate	-	-	183,15	2,13
Acetone	-	-	13,867	0,239
Acetaldehyde	-	-	20,311	0,462
Croton aldehyde	-	-	10,963	0,157
Ethylene diacetate	-	-	14,6	0,1
CO ₂	-	-	8,5	0,193
Total	533,850	16,06	533,848	13,03

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